

Estimating PDFs in Heterogeneous Radar Clutter

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Abstract—Real-world radar resolution cells often contain several terrain types, such that the observed normalized radar cross section of a given clutter cell is an aggregate response from the underlying terrains. These heterogeneous resolution cells create an ill-posed inverse problem in estimating the scattering phenomenology from each terrain type. Assuming the terrain composition of each cell is known (e.g. through Land Use Land Cover maps) and adopting a linear mixing model, we formulate a well-posed but numerically challenging inverse problem. The Markov Chain Monte Carlo technique known as Metropolis Hasting is successfully implemented to extract the underlying Gamma clutter distribution parameters of each terrain type from the heterogeneous clutter cells.

I. INTRODUCTION

Statistical radar clutter models have inherent value for target detection within clutter, as more accurate clutter models yield better threshold placement and provides important inputs to space time adaptive processing and ground moving target indication algorithms. In real-world radar data, large resolution cells may contain several terrain types. We refer to such cells as heterogeneous resolution cells. This paper provides a method for estimating the underlying clutter pdf types and parameters using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method. The method may be used to generate clutter models for a variety of scenarios where measurements of an isolated terrain type are difficult.

II. HETEROGENEOUS CELL MODEL

The goal of this research is to estimate the underlying clutter probability density function (pdf) of each of $m = 1, \dots, M$ terrain types in a scene comprised of $n = 1, \dots, N$ heterogeneous resolution cells. The received normalized radar cross section (NRCS) z_n of each resolution cell is modeled as

$$z_n = \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} d_{n,m}, \quad (1)$$

where $a_{n,m}$ is the proportion of terrain type m in cell n and $d_{n,m}$ is a single realization from the pdf of interest, $f_{D_m}(d)$, in resolution cell n . Equation (1) can be written as $\mathbf{z}_{N \times 1} = \mathbf{A}_{N \times NM} \mathbf{d}_{NM \times 1}$, where \mathbf{A} is a block diagonal matrix of mixing proportions (e.g. known from Land Use Land

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Cover maps) and \mathbf{d} is a vector of NM unknown terrain scatter responses. If $M = 1$, \mathbf{A} is an identity matrix $\mathbf{I}_{N \times N}$, and $z_n = d_{n,m}$. The observations z_n over multiple pure ($M = 1$) cells can be directly used to construct a pdf estimate for terrain type m using maximum likelihood (ML) or other standard pdf-fitting techniques, as is commonly done for monostatic clutter analysis. We consider the problem of heterogeneous clutter mixtures for $M \geq 1$.

III. METHODOLOGY

For $M > 1$, the inverse problem in (1) is intractable. Instead, we assume a Gamma pdf

$$f_{D_m}(d; k_m, \Theta_m) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(k_m) \Theta_m^{k_m}} d^{k_m-1} e^{-\frac{d}{\Theta_m}}, \quad (2)$$

for each terrain type. The goal is to determine the Gamma pdf parameters k_m and Θ_m from the observations z_n . The Gamma pdf has been used in radar due to its physical justification [1] and generality [2]. The Gamma pdf can take the form of other pdfs such as Exponential, Chi-Squared, and Gaussian. Thus, from the estimated values of k_m and Θ_m , we can learn pdf type and parameter values of terrain clutter.

Each observation z_n is a sum of scaled, independent Gamma random variables, the pdf of which cannot be written in closed form [3]. The likelihood for N independent observations of z_n is $p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{k}, \Theta) = \prod_{n=1}^N f_{Z_n}(z_n|\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{k}, \Theta)$ for mixed Gamma pdf $f_{Z_n}(z_n)$ and parameters $\mathbf{k} = k_1, \dots, k_M$ and $\Theta = \Theta_1, \dots, \Theta_M$. ML or maximum a posteriori (MAP) techniques cannot be directly computed to solve for \mathbf{k} and Θ since $f_{Z_n}(z_n)$ has no closed form. A computationally intractable grid search over $2M$ dimensions is required. Instead, we implement the MCMC Metropolis Hastings (MH) algorithm (listed in Algorithm 1), which converges on a posterior pdf $p(\mathbf{k}, \Theta|\mathbf{z})$, from which a MAP estimate can be made.

The MH algorithm operates by proposing a change to each parameter and accepting that change with some probability. The Markov Chain is guaranteed to converge (in infinite iterations) on the posterior pdf if the probability of acceptance is set to the ratio of proposed likelihood to current likelihood [4]. The acceptance probability for a proposed change k_m^* at iteration i is $\alpha_k = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}|k_m^*, \mathbf{k}_{-m}^{(i)}, \Theta^{(i)})}{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{k}^{(i)}, \Theta^{(i)})}$, where $\mathbf{k}_{-m}^{(i)}$ is the current set of $\mathbf{k}^{(i)}$ omitting k_m . Similarly, the acceptance probability for proposed change Θ_m^* is $\alpha_\Theta = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{k}^{(i)}, \Theta_m^*, \Theta_{-m}^{(i)})}{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{k}^{(i)}, \Theta^{(i)})}$. The

Algorithm 1 - Estimation of clutter pdfs in heterogeneous resolution cells.

- Initialize: $\mathbf{k}^{(0)} = \frac{E^2(\mathbf{z})}{\text{Var}(\mathbf{z})}$ and $\Theta^{(0)} = \frac{\text{Var}(\mathbf{z})}{E(\mathbf{z})}$
- For each iteration i of the Markov Chain
 - Randomly select a sample of observations \mathbf{z}^s from \mathbf{z}
 - Randomly select orders to update \mathbf{k} and Θ
 - For each parameter k_m
 - * Create new parameter proposal k_m^* ; accept with probability α_k
 - For each parameter Θ_m
 - * Create new parameter proposal Θ_m^* ; accept with probability α_Θ
 - Check acceptance ratio every 100th MH iteration, adjust transition pdfs to keep acceptance ratio within 25% – 50%
- Stop MH algorithm after user-selected number of iterations
- Estimate parameters: mean of MH Markov chains (omitting burn-in)

proposals k_m^* and Θ_m^* are drawn from a uniform pdf, centered on the current parameter value. To prevent the algorithm from remaining in a local optimum for many iterations, the k_m^* and Θ_m^* pdfs are dynamically updated every 100 iterations to keep the probability of acceptance within 25% – 50% [4].

Computational burden grows with N since $p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{k}, \Theta)$ is computed via an iterative process [3] for every computation of a_k and a_Θ . To decrease computation time, a subset of \mathbf{z} is chosen on each iteration of the MH algorithm. After some burn-in time, the accepted parameter estimates comprise a Markov Chain that varies around the true ML estimate with variance due to sampling \mathbf{z} . The final parameter estimates \mathbf{k} and Θ are taken to be the means of the Markov chains for each parameter (omitting burn-in), as in [5]. A significant decrease in computation time, at the expense of accuracy, can be gained depending on the number of \mathbf{z} values selected on every iteration of MH. When the number of underlying pdfs M is increased, the number of samples from \mathbf{z} selected on each iteration must increase, or the accuracy decreases (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Mean percent error and computation time for random sub-sampling of observations \mathbf{z} in Algorithm 1.

IV. EXAMPLE

We demonstrate the MH algorithm on simulated data with $M = 3$ terrain types. Samples from Exponential, Chi-Squared, and Gaussian pdfs are mixed together in random proportions to form heterogeneous resolution cells. Algorithm 1 is run for 10000 iterations, with 1000 samples of \mathbf{z} randomly selected on each iteration. The estimated Gamma pdfs along with the actual underlying pdfs are shown in Figure 2.

Our goal is to learn the individual terrain pdf types and parameters. Writing down the Gamma pdf model with the estimated parameters, we recognize related pdf forms for the

Fig. 2. MH Gamma Estimate of $M = 3$ underlying non-Gamma clutter pdfs from heterogeneous resolution cells

Exponential and Chi-Squared pdfs as follows:

$$f_{D_1}(d; \hat{k}_1 = 1.02, \hat{\Theta}_1 = 4.90) \approx 0.1999d^{0.2}e^{-\frac{d}{4.90}} \approx \frac{1}{5}e^{-\frac{d}{5}} \quad (\text{Exp. truth}) \quad (3)$$

$$f_{D_2}(d; \hat{k}_2 = 5.03, \hat{\Theta}_1 = 1.99) \approx 0.0012d^{4.03}e^{-\frac{d}{1.99}} \approx \frac{d^{10/2-1}e^{-\frac{d}{2}}}{2^{10/2}\Gamma(\frac{10}{2})} \quad (\chi^2 \text{ truth}) \quad (4)$$

In the limit as $k \rightarrow \infty$ the Gamma pdf can also roughly approximate a Gaussian pdf (specifically, the first two moments are the same) under the Central Limit Theorem [6]. Therefore, noting the large estimated value $\hat{k}_3 = 44.4$, we associate the underlying terrain type with a Gaussian pdf with mean $\hat{k}_3\hat{\Theta}_3 = 21.4 \approx 20$ (Gaussian truth) and variance $\hat{k}_3\hat{\Theta}_3^2 = 10.3 \approx 9$ (Gaussian truth). The associated parameter estimates are near the true values for each of the three terrain types in our simulation. Parameter cutoffs, other pdf types, and pdf associations should be studied more in future work. However, it is promising that given knowledge of how the Gamma pdf generalizes other pdf forms, we can predict the underlying terrain clutter pdf types as well as the parameters from the Gamma pdf k and Θ estimates.

V. CONCLUSION

Under a linear mixing model, the MH algorithm successfully estimates clutter pdfs for multiple terrain types in heterogeneous resolution cells. The algorithm was validated on simulated data. Future work includes testing the algorithm on measured data and developing statistical techniques to learn underlying pdf types from the general Gamma pdf model.

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